

D8.3 Report: Visual Repository & Digital Gallery

Visual Repository of WP8: Best Practices/ of Sports & Arts
Interventions/Programmes across UK, Poland, Israel, Serbia and
Slovenia.

UK

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This document is available for download at <https://dradproject.com/>

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About the Project

D.Rad is a comparative study of radicalisation and polarisation in Europe and beyond. It aims to identify the actors, networks, and wider social contexts driving radicalisation, particularly among young people in urban and peri-urban areas. D.Rad conceptualises this through the I-GAP spectrum (injustice-grievance-alienation-polarisation) with the goal of moving towards measurable evaluations of de-radicalisation programmes. Our intention is to identify the building blocks of radicalisation, which include a sense of being victimised; a sense of being thwarted or lacking agency in established legal and political structures; and coming under the influence of “us vs them” identity formulations.

D.Rad benefits from an exceptional breadth of backgrounds. The project spans national contexts including the UK, France, Italy, Germany, Poland, Hungary, Finland, Slovenia, Bosnia, Serbia, Kosovo, Israel, Iraq, Jordan, Turkey, Georgia, Austria, and several minority nationalisms. It bridges academic disciplines ranging from political science and cultural studies to social psychology and artificial intelligence. Dissemination methods include D.Rad labs, D.Rad hubs, policy papers, academic workshops, visual outputs and digital galleries. As such, D.Rad establishes a rigorous foundation to test practical interventions geared to prevention, inclusion and de-radicalisation.

With the possibility of capturing the trajectories of sixteen nations and several minority nations, the project will provide a unique evidence base for the comparative analysis of law and policy as nation states adapt to new security challenges. The process of mapping these varieties and their link to national contexts will be crucial in uncovering strengths and weaknesses in existing interventions. Furthermore, D.Rad accounts for the problem that processes of radicalisation often occur in circumstances that escape the control and scrutiny of traditional national frameworks of justice. The participation of AI professionals in modelling, analysing and devising solutions to online radicalisation will be central to the project's aims.

Executive Summary/Abstract

New technologies make it increasingly possible for marginalised views to be expressed and shared online and have the potential to span temporal and geographic boundaries that are available to audiences to access from the comfort of their own homes (if one has access to an internet server and technology to act as a vehicle). Likewise, digital, and visual initiatives which showcase the creativity, diversity and community-connectivity of research can envision radically different relationships to their audiences. This report will offer comment on the process of creating our interactive map, and what we can learn and take-away from dissemination techniques of this fashion. The D.Rad interactive map is an innovative and interactive web application that offers a comprehensive and visually appealing roadmap of research findings using data from across 16 countries. It has been created for individuals seeking to explore and understand the world of radical ideologies and deradicalising interventions, including spatial aspects of deradicalisation and social inclusion related arts & sports activities. This transformation of data through a visual lens creates a greater level of inclusivity across target audiences to maximize impact during the lifetime of the project and beyond. For the D.Rad project, these interactive visualisations illustrate trends in radicalisation and best practices with respect to human rights and deradicalisation.

D8.3 presents a digital visualisation showcasing arts and sports activity-led social inclusion programs in five D.Rad countries: Israel, Poland, Serbia, Slovenia, and the UK.

Developing D.Rad D8.3: Visual Repositories and Digital Galleries

Best Practice of Arts & Sports Interventions/programmes across UK, Israel, Poland, Serbia & Slovenia

1. Introduction

With the aim of effectively reaching target audiences, the dissemination and exploitation objectives within a segment of Work Package 8 were directed at developing and consolidating findings into a visual repository. This took the form of an interactive digital map, and the culmination of these efforts is encapsulated in D8.3. This deliverable serves as a comprehensive summary, presenting arts and sports-related social inclusion activities in carefully selected D.Rad sites. The essence of interactive mapping lies in the utilisation of digital imagery presented in map form, facilitating dynamic features such as zooming, panning, and the identification of specific features. This approach not only offers a visually engaging experience but also enables the generation of reports and various means of interacting with or visualising select information on the map. The transformative process of converting data through a visual lens goes beyond traditional methods, ensuring a higher degree of inclusivity across target audiences. This strategic shift aims to maximise the impact of the project not only during its active phase but also well into the future. Specifically, within the D.Rad project these interactive visualisations play a pivotal role in illustrating trends related to radicalisation and highlighting best practices concerning human rights and deradicalisation efforts. In essence, D8.3 represents a synthesis of data, technology, and visual storytelling—a powerful tool that not only conveys information but also engages and informs diverse audiences.

2. Methodology

Country leads from the five national contexts collaboratively gathered a wealth of images and information encapsulating sports and arts-related organisations, programmes, and activities from selected D.Rad sites. In the initial phase, this valuable dataset was integrated into each country's D8.1 report as appendices, providing a comprehensive and detailed documentation of best practices. The collection of images, carefully curated to complement textual information, was a collaborative effort involving country leads, researchers, and D.Rad staff. To enhance the authenticity of the visual content, whenever possible, researchers and project staff contributed their own photographs taken at specific locations within the selected sites. The textual information, constituting an appendix of the D8.1 reports, underwent a subsequent transformation to optimize its utility for map designers. The data was converted into an Excel format, a strategic step taken to facilitate the seamless integration of information into the interactive map at a later stage of the project. This methodical approach ensures that the wealth of data encapsulated in the textual information is translated into a format that aligns with the technical requirements of the map designers, streamlining the process of creating a visually compelling and informative interactive map showcasing the best practices in sports and arts-related activities across diverse D.Rad sites

2.1 Development of Map

Previous map reports provide detailed insights into the creation and evolution of the D.Rad map. As Deliverable 8.3 entered its developmental phases, the map had progressed various developmental processes, undergoing refinements and enhancements. At this point, it had already transitioned to a publicly accessible state, incorporating data derived from Work Packages 3, 4, and 6.

These developmental stages represented a dynamic evolution wherein the map evolved from its conceptualisation to a fully functional and publicly available platform. The integration of data from Work Packages 3, 4, and 6 added layers of comprehensive information, enriching the map's content and expanding its scope. The decision to make the map public at this stage underscored the project's commitment to transparency and

accessibility. It allowed stakeholders, researchers, and the wider community to engage with the evolving insights and data visualisations that the map offered. This strategic move not only marked a milestone in the development of the D.Rad map but also signified a commitment to sharing valuable information related to radicalisation, deradicalisation, and social inclusion on a global scale.

3.Mapping Excellence: D8.3 Best Practices in Arts and Sports for Social Inclusion

The entries featured on the interactive map as part of D8.3 serve as a comprehensive and visually engaging compilation, encapsulating the diverse array of arts and sports-related social inclusion activities in selected D.Rad sites. Specifically focusing on the United Kingdom, Poland, Israel, Serbia, and Slovenia, these entries provide a vibrant representation of best practices within each country. The inclusion of URL links and summarised bios enriches the map's content, offering a multifaceted understanding of various sporting and creative arts activities and programs across these nations.

National partners from Work Package 8 have gone beyond textual descriptions, incorporating images from select programs in the UK, Poland, Israel, Serbia, and Slovenia. This intentional inclusion of visuals serves to infuse a colourful and dynamic element into the inventory of best practice organizations and programs within these countries. The aim is not only to provide information but to create an immersive experience that resonates with diverse audiences. In crafting each entry, the map features five to ten best-practice examples of organisations in each country. This includes detailed information such as biographies, target audiences, and the nature of activities undertaken. Complementing this textual content are one or more pictures capturing the essence of each national setting. To ensure adherence to copyright regulations, project partners diligently clarified the copyright status of these images, either by capturing original photographs or providing suitable references.

The incorporation of visual elements into the map's entries serves a dual purpose. Firstly, it enhances the overall aesthetic appeal, making the information more accessible and engaging for a diverse audience. Secondly, this visual storytelling approach aligns with the

overarching objective of D8.3 — to increase the dissemination and public outreach of best practices in arts and sports-related social inclusion activities. By presenting findings in a visually compelling format, the interactive map becomes a powerful tool in sharing insights, fostering understanding, and catalysing collaborative efforts across borders.

3.1 Accessing Work Package 8 (WP8) data in the D.Rad map.

Visitors to the website's landing page¹ will encounter a clearly labelled tab titled "Interactive Map" (see figure 1). By clicking or pressing on this tab, the viewer will be directed to the map landing page (see figure 2).

Figure 1. D.Rad website landing page. Yellow arrow shows tab for D.Rad map

¹ <https://dradproject.com/visual-repositories-d-rad-interactive-visual-map/interactivemap/>

Figure2 Interactive Map welcome page. The tab to the interactive map is highlighted above by the yellow arrow.

Upon arriving at the map's welcome page, seven tabs are displayed at the top of the page. Viewers can opt for the 'Map' tab, identifiable by a world globe icon, to navigate to the interactive map (see figure 2). Upon accessing the interactive map, users are presented with a global map featuring highlighted D.Rad countries. The left-hand side of the map displays a list of all D.Rad countries. Please be aware that the interactive map exhibits a list of countries that is not exhaustive - and includes only those specifically examined and assessed by members of the D.Rad consortium (Figure 3).

Figure 3 List of D.Rad countries & an explanation of map content detailing the rationale behind the coloured buttons

The description of the map contents provides insight to assist viewers in comprehending and navigating the interactive map (figure 3). The description is as follows:

*The D.Rad interactive map serves as a visually engaging guide for those interested in exploring radicalization and polarization in Europe and the Middle East. As of December 2023, multiple datasets are integrated into this map. **Blue** dots on the map indicate instances of radicalization, offering details about the event type and a summary. **Pink** dots represent stakeholders, their activities, and de-radicalization programs. **Purple** dots highlight select arts and sports-related social inclusion activities in Israel, Poland, Serbia, Slovenia, and the United Kingdom. Lastly, **green** dots signify spatial aspects of deradicalization efforts in Austria, Finland, Georgia, Kosovo, and Italy.*

The various D.Rad work package activity are highlighted in various colours:

- **Blue** – Radical or Extremist Hot Spot Events (D3.8)
- **Pink** – State sponsored & NGO Deradicalisation programmes (D3.8)
- **Green** – Best Practice of arts and sports related social inclusion activities in selected D.Rad sites (D8.3)
- **Purple** - Spatial Aspects of Deradicalisation - Reclaiming Public Space - Interactive Map offers the empirical site-specific findings in consortium partners involved WP9 (D9.3)

Upon selecting specific countries on the map, the user interface shifts the viewer's perspective, facilitated by color-coded buttons. These buttons serve as navigational tools, which are highlighted for clarity. The featured categories encompass 'Events, Deradicalisation Programmes, Best Practice Arts & Sports, and Spatial Aspects of Deradicalisation'. To explore the **purple** and **green** dots on the map, viewers are prompted to initiate a two-step process. Initially, they must engage with the coloured slide button, transitioning from **blue** to **pink**. This action acts as a gateway, allowing the full interface to dynamically switch, revealing data from Deliverables 8.3 and 9.3.

This strategic interface design not only enhances user engagement but also serves as a functional bridge between different layers of information. The deliberate use of colour-coded buttons streamlines the navigation process, ensuring that viewers can seamlessly transition between diverse categories and layers of data representation. In doing so, the interactive map becomes a comprehensive tool, accommodating varied interests and providing a holistic view of the multifaceted research encompassed by D.Rad's deliverables.

3.2 Option for Arabic Translation

The D.Rad map offers users the convenient choice of accessing an Arabic translation. This language option is seamlessly integrated into the welcome page, providing a user-friendly experience for Arabic-speaking audiences (refer to figure 2). As of now, the Arabic translation extends specifically to the welcome page, as depicted in figure 4. This strategic approach aims to enhance inclusivity and accessibility, ensuring that a broader audience, particularly those comfortable with Arabic, can fully engage with the map's content. The commitment to linguistic diversity aligns with D.Rad's broader mission of fostering global engagement and understanding.

Figure 4. Welcome page translated to Arabic.

4. Exploring Best Practices: Arts and Sports-Driven Social Inclusion in Selected D.Rad Sites (D8.3)

In the process of contributing to the collaborative efforts of the D.Rad project, country leads compiled a comprehensive inventory of diverse programs and organisations actively involved in fostering arts and sports-related social inclusion activities. This catalogue is summarised in Appendix 1, a repository that goes beyond mere documentation, offering an overview of programs focused on involving communities and the public. Within these inventories, data is captured, providing a view of organisational activity, geographical locations, overarching aims, target audiences, biographical details, and commencement dates. This multifaceted collection serves as a valuable resource, offering a nuanced

understanding of the approaches and impacts of arts and sports-related social inclusion activities across partner countries.

Figure 5: summary of 8.3 country data

Figure 5 presents a snapshot of the depth and breadth of the data encapsulated within these inventories. The deliberate inclusion of diverse elements ensures that access insights into the scope and diversity of initiatives being undertaken. Notably, this collection of data is documented as appendices within the D8.1 country reports (see appendix 1). This integration ensures that the wealth of information becomes an integral part of the broader documentation, enriching the country-specific reports with valuable insights into the landscape of arts and sports-related social inclusion activities. Consequently, this collaborative effort in cataloguing and documenting initiatives stands as a testament to the project's commitment to comprehensively understanding and showcasing the impactful work undertaken by organisations across partner countries. The resulting inventory becomes a valuable repository, not only for internal project reference but also for viewers seeking a wider understanding of the diverse strategies employed in promoting social inclusion through arts and sports.

The information compiled from the appendices of all D8.1 reports (see appendix 1) and converted into an Excel format (depicted in figure 5) was done to facilitate map designers in coding the content to align with the map requirements. Within this file, there was not only textual data but also a URL link to images to specific organisations. The incorporation of these images introduces an extra visual layer to the map-viewing experience, enhancing viewers' comprehension and appreciation of the activities offered by the documented organisations or programs. The image shown in figure 6 showcases a small collage of images included in 8.3.

Figure 6. Collage showing a collection of images collected as part of D8.3

4.1 D8.3 Map Entries – Visual outcomes

For map designers to effectively categorise images with the associated data entries, each entry and image were assigned a corresponding file number, ensuring easy identification of image-data pairs (see figure 7). Once this process was completed by GCU for all national countries, the data worksheet and its corresponding images were forwarded to the designers. Leveraging their expertise in geospatial data and web development, D.Rad map designers integrated the excel data and visuals from WP8, resulting in the display of organisational locations with informative visual and text pop-ups on the interactive map.

1. Appendix - Israel			
Organization name	Date set up	Image	Copyright/source
1.1 Football 4 Peace-Is	2001	(Figure) 1.1 Football for Peace	© Football for Peace / ht
1.2 kicking Racism and	2003		
1.3 Athena- the centre	2007	(Figure) 1.3 Athena	© AthenaWomen / https
1.4 The LGBT sports clu	2008	(Figure) 1.4 the LGBT sports club Tel Aviv	© The LGBT Sports C;ub /
1.5 The Equalizer Grou	2012	(Figure) 1.5 Queen of the baskets	© The Equalizer Grop / h
1.6 kicking Homophobi	2016		
1.7 Zaza- Community f	2017	(Figure) 1.7 Zaza	© Zaza / https://sconter
1.8 Equal in sport (Shav	2018		
1.9 Mamanet	2005	(Figure) 1.9 Mamanet	© Mamanet / https://ww
1.10 El Halev	2003	(Figure 1) 1.10 El Halev	© ElHalev / https://www

Images as png (below). File names match excel entries above

- 1.1 Football 4 peace
- 1.3 Athena
- 1.4 the LGBT sports club Tel Aviv
- 1.5 the equalizer group
- 1.7 Zaza
- 1.9 Mamanet
- 1.10 El Halev
- 1.10 El Halev_2

Figure 7. image & data entries' corresponding numbers

4.2 Copyright and Source entries.

Some of the images utilized in D8.3 were captured by researchers involved in Work Package 8. However, additional images were obtained from organisational webpages and sites. To ensure proper attribution, copyright and source information is attached to all images, providing accurate credit for their use. According to the UK *Copyright notice: digital images, photographs, and the internet. para:18*, sharing a web link to pages where images have been posted publicly online by the copyright owner is usually not restricted by copyright²

In this context, proper credit has been given to the copyright holders of all images used in D8.3, and source URLs have been included for reference (see appendix 2).

² <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/copyright-notice-digital-images-photographs-and-the-internet/copyright-notice-digital-images-photographs-and-the-internet>

4.3 Interacting with D8.3 on the Map Interface

After choosing a specific country and engaging the 'pink' slider button, users have the opportunity to magnify purple dots, highlighting arts and sports-related social inclusion activities and organizations in more detail. On the left side of the screen, viewers will find comprehensive information about each organization, accompanied by a source link for further reference. Moreover, several entries may include a set of images, providing a visual representation of the showcased activities and initiatives. This feature enhances the user experience, offering both detailed insights and a visual dimension to the exploration of arts and sports-related social inclusion across selected D.Rad sites (see figure 8). This process can be repeated across all countries and cities of interest.

Figure 8. Example of entries from 8.3 data (purple dots). Clicking on these dots opens up visual and textual information to the left of the screen.

5. Knowledge Dissemination through Interactive Visualisation: Bridging Academic and Public Spheres

(What can research practitioners learn from the D.Rad interactive Map?)

Dissemination of knowledge is a process of communicating learned knowledge to target audiences – and visualisation is an efficient tool for the transfer of acquired knowledge. The visualisation of our digital geographies of (de)radicalisation with the visual repository and interactive map offer the public a presentation of complex information in a manner that is inclusive, attractive, and easy to navigate. This ensures that our academic research is not hidden away behind expensive paywalls, but within the grasp of extensive sectors of society. There has never been a time when populations have been more engaged in research, and these visual tools allow researchers and scholars the ability to share knowledge freely across social and geographical boundaries – and in turn, narrow the gap between the academically positioned and the community-positioned knowledge forums³ Disseminations of this visual variety break across social borders, and reach right into the heart communities and invoke new ways of reaching and actively involving audiences who would otherwise remain out of reach for traditional methods of communication. The utilisation of interactive visualisation tools, such as visual repositories and interactive maps, facilitates the presentation of complex information in a manner that is not only inclusive but also captivating and user-friendly. Gone are the days when academic research was confined behind expensive paywalls, making it accessible only to a select few. Now, through these visual mediums, extensive sectors of society can engage with and benefit from the wealth of knowledge generated by scholarly endeavours. The impact of disseminating knowledge through interactive visualisation goes beyond mere accessibility. It introduces new and innovative ways to actively involve audiences who may have

³ Lassiter, Luke Eric. 2005. *The Chicago Guide to Collaborative Ethnography*. Chicago, London: University of Chicago Press.

remained out of reach through traditional communication methods. By presenting digital geographies of (de)radicalisation through visual means, this approach engages diverse communities, sparking interest, understanding, and fostering a more collaborative and informed society.

Appendix 1

5-10 arts /sports programmes in your own national country that are specifically designed to challenge aspects of social isolation.

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1. Israel

Organisation Name	Date set up	Bio	Place	Activity	Target Group	Aims	Source
<p>1.1 Football 4 Peace-Israel</p>	<p>2001</p>	<p>(NGO) It began in peripheral villages in Northern Israel, setting up basic football coaching camps for Jewish and Arab youths. since 2011, it also operates in southern Negev in partnership with the German Sports University, the British Council, and the IFA. From 2009-2012 it was funded by the European Union. In 2013 a new NGO, Sport Unites, began working with the IFA, inheriting and adapting the F4P model</p>	<p>International Tel Aviv Local</p>	<p>"Off-pitch manual" activities- getting children to enjoy learning and playing football together in non-threatening settings. The idea is to underpin the technical football coaching programme and manual with the values and principles that help promote mutual understanding and inclusive citizenship.</p> <p>"On-pitch manual" activities- designed as a guide for coaches who recognise the potential of football as a medium through which to teach positive personal values</p>	<p>Jewish and Arab Youths, Teenagers, and kids from the geographic and demographic peripheral areas</p>	<p>One of the guiding principles of F4P is that simply playing football is not sufficient to promote the kind of interaction that can allow longer-term relationships and cross-community understanding to flourish.</p>	<p>https://www.football4peace.org.uk/projects/israel/</p>

		for a broader application beyond football in the latest "Sport 4 Life project".		that laid the foundations for enhanced inter-community relations. It is adopted by school Physical Education lessons and sports clubs, where Fair Play is promoted. Events- Peace Education on the Korean Peninsula and for Social Justice' inclusion' events in Europe, such as the F4P v Homophobia Festivals with the Justin Fashanu Campaign.			
1.2 Kicking Racism and Violence out of the fields (KRV)	2003	(NGO) Founded by the New Israel Fund (NIF), promoted by the IFA, as a project that funds games and activities against racism in football. In 2016 it announced that	Jerusalem, Herzliya, Tel Aviv-Jaffa, Hifa	The NGO holds Conferences, suggests supportive grants, and works on social media awareness through posts and podcasts. It also participates in parliament	Jewish and Arab football clubs, football fans	aims to eradicate racism and violence from the football fields, believing that a change	. https://nif.org.il/kickitout-con-one/

		against the deterioration of relations between Jews and Arabs, KRV would give local football teams and fan organisations grants of 100,000 NIS for acting on the topic. Its first national conference took place in 2022.		communities' debates, providing data.		that begins on the football fields will permeate the rest of society.	
1.3 Athena- the centre for progressing women sports in Israel	2007	(NGO) operates professional multiyear programs intended to create opportunities for girls, young women, and women in sports, with dedicated programs at sports associations and bodies (defined by standards), programs at authorities, and sports clubs and federations.	Tel Aviv Also local	Athena acts to recruit, retain, and promote girls, young women, and women in various sports. They start from elementary school, at local authorities, and close to home (15 localities). Its projects help recruit and retain new athletes, create competition, and develop new opportunities for girls	Girls, young women, and women in sports	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establishing a quantitative and qualitative foundation for female athletes across Israel. 2. Creating women's leadership in sports – Appropriate representation 	https://www.athenawomen.org.il/english/

		<p>It first started with connecting to local authorities to grow the base of the pyramid of women's sports in Israel, expand the infrastructure for women's sports, and create more opportunities to recruit and retain girls in various sports.</p>		<p>at the participating club/association.</p> <p>So far- 25 of this type (2022).</p> <p>Programs are oriented for all ages, from elementary school to elite competitive levels, as part of the select competitive sports programs in all sports bodies; It promotes discourse on women's issues in sports and places this content on the agenda through conferences, forums, and meetings; It offers a broad portfolio of enrichment tools via such projects as Athena Plus and Athena Ambassadors;</p> <p>"Athena Plus" program - enrichment lectures by</p>		<p>of women among decision-makers and policy leaders in sports, ensuring appropriate and egalitarian budgets, resource allocations, and management by decision-makers. 3. Education to change public opinion in Israel society as to the importance of sports as a critical factor in the training and development of</p>	
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				professionals in the fields of sports for female athletes at all levels; "Athena is walking far"- dominant national festival in each municipality, including dozens of thousands of women walking and running together (15,000 participants in Tel Aviv only in 2017).		each girl and young woman	
1.4 The LGBT sports club Israel	2008	Established as a small club in Tel Aviv, this organisation is the only LGBTQ+ organisation in Israel engaged with the world of sports. It is a member of international LGBTQ+ sports federations. It holds critical messages, declaring that sport is for	Semi-national (Tel Aviv-Jaffa, Haifa, Jerusalem, Ramat H'ashron)	The LGBTQ+ Sports Club will work to promote and strengthen the integration between the LGBTQ+ community and the world of sports (While empowering its members, professionalising them and creating a community fabric between them). Their shared values include	LGBTQ+, people with a particular sexual preference, students or young people, and others.	A proud sports club leads the fight against Homophobia in sports on four levels: 1. Explanation. 2. Education for tolerance. 3. Promoting LGBTQ+	https://twitter.com/tlvlgbt sports?lang=en

		<p>everyone, including the LGBTQ+ community; there is no contradiction between belonging to the community and engaging in sports, and no room for Homophobia. It is supported in part by the Ministry of the treasury. Its directive board includes athletes from academia, sports, businesses and the public sector. In recent years it expanded to additional cities.</p>		<p>creating and maintaining sports teams for the community.</p> <p>Encouraging social connections as part of engaging in sports. Offering a social framework for all ages, which is not based on entertainment and is not based on support groups, etc.</p>		<p>visibility in sports. 4. Changing regulations and legislation.</p>	
<p>1.5 The Equalizer Group (Shaar L'shivyon)</p>	<p>2012</p>	<p>The NGO program operates football teams and learning centres where participants receive assistance with homework and test prep and have educational</p>	<p>Semi-national Tel Aviv the Galilee region of the North</p>	<p>Educational sports activities. The activity focuses on the social and geographic periphery in Israel to give children, girls and teenagers a robust framework for personal</p>	<p>Teenagers, kids from the geographic and demographic peripheral areas</p>	<p>Create social, gender and geographical equality through programs combining team</p>	<p>https://en.the-equalizer.org/s-haar-shivyon/</p>

		<p>activities that instil values and strengthen the team spirit. It activates thousands of kids and teenagers participating in sports activities near their living area while containing inclusive agendas for different sectors. It funds itself via contributions from private and public businesses, educational facilities and sports public and private actors.</p>	<p>the Negev region in the south, Tel Aviv, Dimona, Haifa, Ramat H'ashron, Afoula, Jerusalem</p>	<p>development and assimilating values such as tolerance, mutual respect, preventing violence and eradicating racism while creating a bridge between different populations in Israeli society. All teams in the program attend a festive monthly regional tournament. Players are selected by the school or community centre based on their familiarity with the participants.</p> <p>The activities include weekly soccer practice, social activities, and monthly tournaments in which 12 regional teams meet to celebrate sports spirit and values.</p>		<p>sports with educational activities. It also aims to empower and develop teens, equip them with new skills, and expose them to global content that will help form and solidify their dreams and aspirations for the future.</p>	
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				<p>The participants must conduct themselves appropriately at school and the community centres, with a direct link between school staff, the coach, and the social coordinator.</p> <p>It holds five central programmes that manifest its aim within peripheral localities across the country: The equaliser (Shaar L'shivyon), "Boatot", "The 48ers", "Special goals", and "safe swimmer".</p>			
1.6 kicking Homophobia out of the fields	2016	This sub-initiative emerged from the KRV program of the New Israel Fund (NIF). Following UEFA awareness month in the	International, local (Herzliya)	Activity includes playing annually against LGBTQ+ teams and reporting to the IFA regarding incidents of Homophobia, including within football clubs.	LGBTQ+ players, judges, and fans.	It attracts crowds from different sectors and raises awareness of	

		fight against Homophobia, the IFA is compelling the topic via games.		"Rainball" - established in 2012; works according to an English model, with about 100 members. Its principles are fairness, tolerance, mutual respect and equality regardless of religion, race, sex or gender.		tolerance and acceptance of LGBTQ+ football participants.	
1.7 Zaza-Community for the Promotion of Women's Sports	2017	(NGO) Zaza (meaning "moving") association arose out of the area of Jerusalem, out of a real need for women to find a place to play leading sports in the country (football, basketball, volleyball). The players turned to the Jerusalem municipality and realised a need for a broader change within Jerusalem and the attitude towards	Semi-national (North, Centre, South) - Beer Sheva, Tel Aviv, The western Negev region (Sderot), Haifa, Jerusalem, Binyamina	Today they help promote sports practice - help to find fields, an educational program to increase exposure to team sports among girls at a young age, and establishing WhatsApp groups for the various sports. We try to connect women who want to play. It holds communal gatherings involving sports, such as in the 2022 Euro cup- the game with the	Local populations, the general public, children and youth, women, students	1. Promoting, encouraging and leveraging popular sports, achievements and challenges, body culture and a healthy lifestyle among women in various settings of all ages and all sectors, 2. Organising,	. https://www.fac ebook.com/zaz awomen/about

		<p>women's sports.</p> <p>Following the success in finding fields, Zaza's operation began to spread, and more women began to contact the association with a request to help them find areas for games throughout their cities.</p> <p>The association is a community promoting women's sports that have been working for several years to turn women's sports into a legitimate consumer product. It created a network of women athletes involved in practical and educational solutions for practising sports.</p>		<p>most significant number of participants; Zaza organised a meeting to watch the game and spread women's football.</p>		<p>managing and running sports initiatives and competitions for women in various branches. 3. Supporting women's sports associations and organisations, 4. Financing resources for women's sports, providing scholarships for sports initiatives, and for women who wish to engage in sports.</p>	
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1.8 Equal in sport (Shavim B'Sport)	2018	This innovative program of the Ministry of Culture and Sports and "Joint Israel" (NGO) intends to promote opportunities for people with physical, cognitive or mental disabilities to engage in adapted and regular physical activity near their homes. It Cooperates with many private and non-profit organisations and the	Netanya, Beer-Sheva, Akko, Umm El Fahim, and the Emek Heffer Regional Council.	Municipalities get funds and then operate sports programs with similar approaches and facilities adjusted to athletes with disabilities according to the proximity of the desired sports facilities. Five authorities work it by using special programs that combine special needs athletes with regular ones, by adopting the adjustments and	Adults and teenagers aged 15 and over who live in the community, people with physical, cognitive or mental disabilities, and Special needs in Jewish and Arab municipalities	The main aim is to increase the number of people with disabilities who engage in sports regularly in the community to improve their health and sense of mental well-being (Well Being). It aims	Equal in sport (Shavim B'Sport) - https://schoolsp.ort.co.il/%D7%A9%D7%95%D7%99%D7%9D-%D7%91%D7%A4%D7%95%D7%A8%D7%98/

		Israeli Disabled Sports Association.		accessibility to sports structures and environment. The local schools and community centres publish it.		to promote achievements in competitive sports for people with disabilities, to create an infrastructure that allows every person with a disability to choose an adapted physical activity from various possibilities and lead to a positive change of attitudes of the entire population towards people with disabilities.	
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<p>1.9 Mamanet</p>	<p>2005</p>	<p>The first ever communal mothers. Mamanet has established the third biggest sports field of "netball" in Israel. Netball is a team ball game, similar to a volleyball game. The game is popular among women, girls and girls. Mamanet is the largest social sports league specifically for mothers in Israel. Its establisher initiated the first team through municipality support. It has gathered mothers through their children's schools to meet once a week for a game. It has become the only sports league for thousands of mothers in a few years. Mamanet is a part of the</p>	<p>International (Austria, Italy, Greece, Cyprus & the US and more)</p> <p>National (Kfar Saba, Yerucham, Galilee region of the North, the Negev region in the south</p> <p>Haifa, Jerusalem, Beer Sheva;</p> <p>Kfar Saba, Yerucham ("The Desert Foxes"), Haifa, Jerusalem, Beer</p>	<p>Mamanet allows mothers to revive their younger days as athletes or experience being part of a sports league. Mothers of students play in a league that holds awards. In doing so, they represent their children's school with sportsmanship. The association is based on children's elementary, junior high and high schools. It progresses social connection development as part of the communal perception of assisting each member in all aspects of life (e.g., annual tournaments for breast cancer prevention, COVID-19 support groups, and more.</p>	<p>Mothers and adult women (ages 30 and above) run across all populations, such as secular ultra-orthodox immigrants, newcomers etc.</p>	<p>To supply a model for a combination of sports and community, demonstrating school pride, good sportsmanship, friendly and professional competition, fair play & positive physical activity.</p>	<p>Mamanet</p> <p>https://www.mamanet.org.il/viewArticle_en.asp?id=192</p>
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		CSIT World Sports Games (International Workers and Amateurs in Sports Confederation) since 2017. https://www.mamanet.org.il/viewArticle_en.asp?id=192	Sheva, Omer, Holon, Tamra 90 cities in total).				
1.10 EI Halev	2003	The NGO is the Israeli representative and the global movement leader for 'empowering self-defence (ESD) and exports knowledge and expertise. It trains women of all ages and sectors in preventing sexual, emotional and physical violence through educational programs of empowering self-defence, which provide tools to increase	Jerusalem, Tel Aviv-Jaffa, Rishon LeZion, Ramat Gan, Rehovot, Petach Tiqwa, Modiin, Lod, Kefar Saba, Beer Shemesh, Beer Sheva, the North region.	The association operates within hundreds of organisations, municipal authorities, business companies, associations and educational, health and welfare institutions. It seeks to create a society that respects each person's right to life, liberty and personal security.	Children, youth, women, people with disabilities, minority groups (Ultra-orthodox, Arab women, LGBTQ+), and older people from all sectors of Israeli society, Backlash populations.	It has two goals. 1. teaching personal safety and empowering self-defence skills. 2. Raising awareness and achieving significant and sustainable social change.	https://www.elhalev.org/about

		confidence, discover personal resilience, manage conflicts and deal with various risk situations. https://www.elhalev.org/about					
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2. Poland

Organisation Name	Date set up	Bio	Place	Activity	Target Group	Aims	Source
2.1 'Never Again' Association, Polish Football Association	1996	The problem of racism and discrimination is	Poland	Removing fascist/racist symbolism	Football fans, players, coaches, referees, sports activists	Promoting anti-racist attitudes among football fans	https://www.nigdywiecej.org/o-nas/nasze-

		<p>still an issue in football.</p> <p>The project 'Let's Kick Racism out of Football Stadiums' has been initiated by Marcin Kornak, football fan and a founder of the "NEVER AGAIN" Association that aims to prevent racism and xenophobia.</p>		from stadiums.	and journalists.		inicjatywy/wykopmy-rasizm-ze-stadionow .
2.2 Ministry of Sport and Tourism	Unknown	'Football Fans Together'	Currently there are 18 local branches of the project	Education of football fans against violence, racism and	Football fans	It aims to develop empathy, civic virtues and 'positive patriotism' without xenophobia.	https://kibice-razem.pl

				intolerance			
2.3 Foundation for Freedom	2004	'Etnoliga' was founded by the Foundation for Freedom whose mission is to 'develop an open society by supporting and stimulating vulnerable groups regardless their origin, skin colour, gender, or religion'.	Warsaw	Football games	Mostly migrants	Creating an environment where people can play football free from racism, sexism and homophobia.	https://www.etnoliga.org/en/ .
2.4 Ministry of Administration and Digitisation	Unknown	'Partnership for Active Estates' was initiated to integrate and educate the local	Bialystok	Civic education on diversity through	Local residents and students.	Intergenerational cooperation and increasing the sense of acceptance for the	https://www.prezydent.pl/archiwum-bronislawa-komorowskiego/witryna-

		community in a region prone to radicalization.		arts and sport.		diversity and multiculturalism among local people.	obywatelska/witryna-obywatelska/projekt.284.html .
2.5 Fans' Association Pogon Szczecin "Portowcy"	2020	'Niepełnosprawni niewykluczeni' ('People with disabilities not excluded') was an initiative of Fans' Association Pogon Szczecin "Portowcy" to include those football fans who live with a disability.	Szczecin	purchase of a specially adapted bus for fans of Pogoń Szczecin who live with a disability	Football fans of Pogon Szczecin who have a disability	Involvement of football fans of Pogon Szczecin who have a disability in its activities so that they can actively participate in fan life.	

3. Serbia

Title	Institution(s), Place	Aims	Source	PLACE
<p>3.1 <i>Virtual Becomes Reality</i></p> <p>*this initiative is part of CoE's campaign <i>No Hate Speech Movement</i></p>	CSO Libero	Prevention of digital violence; educational programmes focused on children and youth	link	Online
<p>3.2 Trening <i>Zaustavimo govor mržnje</i> (Training <i>Let's stop hate speech</i>)</p> <p>*this action is part of Serbian National</p>	Krovna organizacija mladih Srbije i Institut za medije i različitosti Zapadni Balkan	Raising youth's awareness of hate speech consequences; offering broader understanding of freedom of expression and hate speech; training for peer educators	https://koms.rs/2017/08/03/odrzana-obuka-zaustavimo-govor-mrznje/	Online

Campaign against Hate Speech				
3.3 <i>Anonimna mržnja</i> (<i>Anonymous Hatred</i>)	CSOs Belgrade Centre for Human Rights and LIBER New Media Centre	Raising public awareness about online hate speech and suggesting the mechanisms for countering hate speech, particularly the responsibility and punishment policy	https://www.bgcentar.org.rs/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/anonimna-mrznja.jpg	Belgrade
3.4 Sandžak: POLITIKE IDENTITETA I PREVENCIJA EKSTREMIZMA, mart 2020. (helsinki.org.rs)	Helsinki Committee for Human Rights	Theatre play	https://www.helsinki.org.rs/serbian/doc/identitetske%20politike%20sandzak.pdf	Novi Pazar
3.5 Resilience: Civil Society for Media Free of Hate and Disinformation	SEENPM	Six tv shows that reflects research results	https://seenpm.org/about-resilience/	

3.6 Youth Leadership Programme	PIN	express oneself through a song, a video or online content	https://psychosocialinnovation.net/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/ONLINE-TRAINING-PROGRAM-ON-YOUTH-LEADERSHIP_fin.pdf	Online
3.7 Pozorišna predstava „Kako ja ovo sinu da objasnim?“	Centar E8	The play talks about extremism, how it occurs and what are its consequences. From ethnic, religious to the very radical non-acceptance of those different from oneself, extremism is becoming a big problem in today's society.	http://e8.org.rs/pr-evencija-nasilnog-ekstremizma/	<u>Belgrade, theatre play travelled through Serbia</u>
3.8 Svi u glas!	Choir Svi u Glas	A choir started for ethnic Roma children at risk of poverty has grown into a musical-educational platform that	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T3NhLUmhT9s	<u>Perform all around Serbia</u>

		connects all those interested in singing, listening – and understanding each other.		
3.9 Café Bar Sixteen	Kafe bar 16	Cafe Bar 16 in Cetinjska Street in Belgrade is, just at first glance, a cafe like any other. Apart from good coffee and the smiles of the employees, it offers much more than that – work and security for young people from Svratishte, who mostly live in extreme poverty.	https://www.rts.rs/lat/vesti/drustvo/4120565/kafe-bar-16-nije-obican-kafic-potrebna-mu-je-vasa-pomoc-kako-bi-opstao.html	<u>Belgrade</u>

4. Slovenia –

Organisation Name	Date set up	Bio	Place	Activity	Target Group	Aims
4.1 APIS Institute	Organisation: 2012 / Programme 2019-2020	We are a multimedia institute fostering collaboration among vulnerable groups, artists, experts, and the public. Through workshops and creative approaches, we support social inclusion efforts. We explore socially engaged content through art, promoting awareness, reflection,	Ljubljana	<i>Multivision</i> project trained 50 members of vulnerable groups in multimedia, dance, and theatre, with the goal of enhancing their employment opportunities in the cultural sector and promoting social inclusion. Through innovative artistic	Immigrants, refugees, unaccompanied minors (over 15 years old), asylum seekers, and people with disabilities	Training: To provide training in multimedia, theatre, and dance to 50 members of vulnerable groups / Social Inclusion: To promote social inclusion of vulnerable groups by

		dialogue, and empathy as core human values.		expressions, the project activities addressed the patterns of stigmatization based on differences (culture, disability, immigration, and asylum) and explored how artistic forms can be used as tools for empowerment, acquiring new skills for better employability, mobilization, motivation, and	s and impairment; members of ethnic communities and former Yugoslav nations residing in Slovenia	empowering them through artistic forms. / Intersectional Approach: The project takes an intersectional approach, recognizing the complex and layered identities of vulnerable groups./ Empowerment and Mobilization: Aims to inspire
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				<p>encouraging proactive engagement of vulnerable groups.</p>		<p>proactive engagement, motivation, and active participation in social and cultural activities.</p> <p>/ Employment Opportunities : By providing training, the project aims to enhance the employability of vulnerable individuals in the cultural sector. Advoc</p>
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						acy and Awareness: The project aims to raise awareness about the challenges faced by vulnerable groups, promote dialogue, and advocate for policies and practices that support their rights and well-being.
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<p>4.2 Association for Culture and Education PiNA</p>	<p>Organisation : 1998 / Programme: 2018</p>	<p>PiNA builds connections. Between individuals and their need for co-creation. Between a team and project language, to unite political, professional and societal dimensions. Between society and its challenges in this century.</p> <p>PiNA is promoting socially responsible practices and strengthening the culture of dialogue. It serves as a point for meeting, providing information,</p>	<p>Based in Koper, SW Slovenia. Working in Coastal-Karst region, Slovenian Istra.</p>	<p><i>Theatre of the Oppressed:</i> Creating theatre plays that present life situations and discriminatory practices, followed by possible interventions that address them.</p> <p>Legislative theatre for advocacy action where proposals for measures are presented to</p>	<p>LGBTIQ+ population and people with migrant background.</p>	<p>Social inclusion and inclusion into the labour market. Enforcement of collective rights.</p>
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		exchange, connection and collaboration in the field of societal challenges.		the municipal authorities.		
4.3 Kick Racism	2008	Kick Racism is part of a wider, non-formal and self-organised initiative that promotes the fight against all forms of exclusion, hatred and oppression through sports and builds alternatives through such events.	Tournament takes place in Ljubljana, the capital of Slovenia and brings together participants from whole Slovenia and wider region (CRO, IT)	Football tournament	Socially and economically marginalized groups, such as migrants, homeless, and majority population - all	The tournament is an opportunity to meet, connect and build solidarity between different groups and socially engaged initiatives and people

					ages and genders.	who have been pushed to the social margins by the existing system. It is an open community space of radical equality that rejects racism, sexism, homophobia, nationalism and all other forms of
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						discrimination.
4.4 Ljubljana Pride Association	Programme: 2013 and 2020	The Purpose of the Ljubljana Pride Association is to contribute to the establishment of a society that will be non-discriminatory, inclusive and open to all individuals, regardless of their gender, sexual orientation, sexual identity or any other personal circumstance. It was established with the aim of safeguard the human rights and interests of the lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, intersex	Country wide.	<i>Decontamination: Mapping hate speech or discriminatory speech graffiti and its transformations into positive, inclusive and creative messages.</i>	Marginalised groups that are more often targets of hate speech, negative stereotypes and stigmatisation, such as LGBTIQ+, refugees,	Monitoring what is happening on the streets and providing a space for inspiration to respond to hatred with street art.

		and queer (LGBTIQ+) population. The association acts as a youth, voluntary, independent and non-profit civil society organization.			immigrants, people of colour, and Muslims.	
4.5 Oloop, institution for contemporary textile art and design	Organisation : 2003 / Programme: 2019	Oloop works in many different fields of visual arts – product design, spatial design, textile art etc. They conduct educational activities (lectures, workshops) and connect design with socially engaged projects.	Based in Ljubljana, the capital of Slovenia.	<i>Story of Women</i> is a project on textile and spiritual journey of women of various ages, nationalities, religious background, and life circumstances. They create symbols that form	Women with migrant background.	Art and creation are used as a tool of empowerment and communication, as well as a means of mobilizing, motivating and encouraging

				<p>a large embroidered textile wall.</p> <p><i>Selfies:</i></p> <p>Embroidered autoportraits are made by women who come from different parts of the world - Albanians from Kosovo and North Macedonia, Iraqis, Iranians, Moroccans, Syrians and Kurds.</p>		<p>proactive action by users. The purpose of the exhibitions is, among other things, to pave the way from feelings of loneliness and incomprehensibility to feelings of belonging and inclusion.</p>
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<p>4.6 Penitentiary Institutions and Juvenile Correctional Facility</p>	<p>Institution: 1991</p>	<p>The main mission of the Administration for the Enforcement of Criminal Sanctions is to ensure the execution of criminal sanctions, including pretrial detention, imprisonment, substitute imprisonment, and educational measures involving placing a minor in a juvenile correctional facility. We ensure the comprehensive enforcement of the rights and obligations of incarcerated</p>	<p>Covering the whole territory of Slovenia – Institutions based in Dob, Ig, Celje, Koper, Nova Gorica, Ljubljana, Novo mesto, Maribor, Murska Sobota, Rogoza, Radeče.</p>	<p>In all institutions and departments, sports and recreational activities are prevalent, and various creative activities also play an important role. Convicts and minors participate in various sports activities (fitness, indoor soccer, basketball, table tennis, volleyball,</p>	<p>Incarcerated individuals, minors and adults.</p>	<p>To enable the possibility of resocialization of incarcerated individuals into society. To organize the treatment of incarcerated individuals in such a way that they are trained for life in freedom and deterred</p>
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		<p>individuals and the development of various forms and methods of working with incarcerated individuals.</p>		<p>bocce, chess, darts, badminton, running, walks), and various tournaments are organized (chess, bocce, table tennis, soccer, volleyball). Creative workshops include painting, modeling, clay, Fimo and plaster modelling, literary workshops and individual</p>		<p>from repeating criminal offenses, so that they can live according to valid legal and moral norms after serving their sentences.</p>
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				instrument playing.		
4.7 Society for help and self-help of the homeless Kings of the Street	Organisation : 2005 / Programme 2007	The Society for Aid and Self-Help of Homeless People "Kralji ulice" is an independent non-governmental humanitarian organization with non-profit objectives. It brings together experts and individuals who deal with homelessness and related phenomena, as well as individuals who experience homelessness and	Based in Ljubljana, the capital of Slovenia, and Maribor, the second largest city. A part of the programme – distribution of newspaper "Kings of the Street" covers the whole country.	Homeless football team which collaborates with the Ljubljana Sports Association and Poljane Sports Club, as well as Olimpija Sports Club. It is invited to various sports and social events in Slovenia and other EU countries. In	Homeless and other socially excluded groups of the population.	Constructive resolution of disputes. Reducing tolerance for racism and increasing tolerance. Raising self-confidence of socially excluded individuals.

		<p>the associated social exclusion. They are committed to studying, understanding, and researching homelessness, preventing homelessness, improving the living conditions of homeless men and women, developing practical forms of work in the field of homelessness, and engaging in journalistic activities in this field.</p>		<p>addition to football, they also organize other sports and recreational activities tailored to the abilities of beneficiaries, such as table tennis, chess, and exclusively for women, martial arts and stretching exercises.</p>		
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<p>4.8 Society for Sustainable Development Terra Verra</p>	<p>2011</p>	<p>Terra Verra has been figuring out circus shenanigans, researching, walking, dreaming, gathering stories in urban and rural landscapes, and above all paving the way for interpersonal solidarity. They scrape the surface of the streets and forest paths so that we can penetrate to living voices, to those that are too distant, not loud enough, or simply too different to be heard in the textbook versions of history. They are interested in</p>	<p>Based in Kostanjevica na Krki, SE Slovenia. Working in a Slovenian-Croatian border region of Gorjanci-Žumberak, and in Ljubljana.</p>	<p>Rural and Urban Migrantour: development of new narratives about migration and cultural heritage in the local area, which are presented to the visitors by tour guides with migrant background. People from the local environment and beyond discover intercultural influences</p>	<p>People with migrant background, local population in the border region and the capital city, tourists.</p>	<p>Enhancing social inclusion through a creative use of cultural heritage. Fostering upskilling of immigrants and refugees, and developing a sense of belonging.</p>
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		the relationships between centers and peripheries; and are critical of the centers when they try to dominate.		together with the guides, broaden their horizons and at the same time reduce stereotypes and prejudices. Direct contact and a positive mutual experience are crucial.		
4.9 The Bob Institute	Organisation : 2007 / Youth centre Ulca	The Bob Institute is an NGO active in the field of youth work, with the aim to provide conditions	Based in Ljubljana, the capital of Slovenia. Providing	<i>Ulca ("Street") School :</i> activities in Youth Centre Ulca that	Youth from 15 to 29 y.o. from vulnerabl	Developing interests, talents, opportunities for

	<p>(“Street”): 2016</p>	<p>for development autonomy of young people, increase the active participation of young people in society and encourage them to think critically. Its mission is to "Ensure active participation in society, especially those who do not have a public voice or whose voice is not heard." Youth work is based on street-based youth work and field work, and activities of youth centres with</p>	<p>trainings and passing on good practices to youth organizations throughout Slovenia</p>	<p>include classes of breakdance, street art (graffiti, murals), music production (DJ-ing, beatmaking), and lyric in rhymes (MC, rap).</p>	<p>e groups, such as NEET youth (youth not in education, employment or training) - school dropouts, unemployed, youth with an experience of homeless</p>	<p>creative leisure time activities (as a means of prevention), developing critical and proactive thinking skills, Encouraging active participation of young people in shaping their social environment</p>
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		<p>emphasis on creative leisure time.</p>			<p>ness, LGBTIQ+ youth, youth with migrant background, youth with mental health disorders.</p>	<p>Expanding knowledge and training flexibility of thinking, as well as increasing the ability to successfully manage daily life challenges,</p> <p>Building skills and strengthening competencies that are essential to independent shaping of</p>
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						life goals, acquiring functional knowledge, and active citizenship.
4.10 The Tri Institute	Organisation : 2014 / Programme in 2018	The Tri Institute is a non-governmental organisation for sustainable community practices. Institute's main focus is on the development of other non-governmental organisations and civil society. The content is focused on empowering women from all parts	Based in Škofja Loka, NW Slovenia. Fostering, organising, and implementing sustainable community practices in the area of Škofja Loka, the Gorenjska	<i>Engaged intercultural knitting community:</i> Establishing creative (knitting) support groups and conducting socially engaged interventions to address, among others, the	Women with migrant background.	To offer women from other cultural backgrounds an opportunity to learn Slovene and engage in creative activities together with their

		<p>of the world and developing collaborative processes within the community.</p>	<p>region, and elsewhere.</p>	<p>challenges of migration, inclusion, and intercultural coexistence. Conducting workshops for the creative use of wool and Slovene language courses.</p>		<p>creative counterparts from the community. To bring together a rewarding craft creativity and the feeling of inclusion and participation in society. Community creative activities, especially community knitting,</p>
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						may be used as a powerful tool in the two-way process of integration and in addressing the challenges of intercultural coexistence.
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5. UK

Organisation Name	Date set up	Bio	Place	Activity	Target Group	Aims	Source
5.1.Street Soccer Scotland	2009	SSS use football to create positive change in the lives of socially disadvantaged adults and young people in Scotland	Aberdeen, Edinburgh, Glasgow, Greenock Dundee, Motherwell, Scotland, UK.	Drop-in Football sessions, mental health support & skills development. 2023 will see teams from Wales, Scotland, England & N. Ireland will travel to Sacramento, California, USA to participate in the Homeless World Cup	socially disadvantaged groups across Scotland: Individuals who have experience(d) homelessness, addiction, mental health challenges, social isolation, or/& the justice system.	Street Soccer provide free football-themed training & personal development opportunities for socially disadvantaged groups across Scotland. Their underlying principles are founded on	https://streetsoccerscotland.org/

						relationships and purpose	
5.2. Achieve More	-	Achieve More Scotland delivers programmes to improve young people's physical and mental health and well-being, confidence and self-esteem, aspirations, personal responsibility and life chances by engaging them in structured, positive activities that work across	Glasgow, Scotland, UK			Leading and empowering children and young people from Scotland's most deprived communities to enhance life chances.	https://aan.dm.org.uk/

		communities and are delivered by role models.					
5.3. Leap Sports	2013	Leap works for greater inclusion for LGBTI people in sport and against homophobia, biphobia and transphobia in a sports context. We are committed to breaking down the structural, social and personal barriers which prevent lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and intersex (LGBTI) people across the country from	Edinburgh, Glasgow, Inverness, Livingstone, Lossiemouth, Nairn, Perth, West Lothian, Scotland, UK	Team & Individual sports clubs	LGBTI people	Leadership, Equality and Active Participation in Sports for LGBTI people in Scotland)	https://leap.sports.org/

		accessing, participating and excelling in Scottish sports.					
5.4. Creative Stirling	2012	Creative Stirling objectives are to assert change through enterprise, arts and culture - working with and for all of Stirling's diverse communities.	Stirling, Scotland	Creative arts workshops & community engagement activities	Children & Adults – including disadvantaged communities & groups	Providing Community arts based programmes to marginalised groups, including, LGBTI youth, refugees groups,	https://www.creativesirling.org/
5.5. Heavy Sound Project	2015	Heavy Sound transforms the lives of vulnerable and disengaged people across East Lothian, Midlothian and	Edinburgh, Scotland	Music, sport, film-making & mentoring programmes	vulnerable, disadvantaged and disengaged young people	Heavy Sound makes learning work for vulnerable, disadvantaged and disengaged young people, re-engaging them through	https://www.heavysound.org/

		<p>Edinburgh improving their health, wellbeing and capability by teaching them new skills in music, biking, sports, life skills and mentoring, leading them to become contributing citizens with positive pathways to future destinations.</p>				<p>innovative projects involving hip hop and rapping, song writing, DJ'ing and mixing tuition, electronic music production, sound recording, graphic design and film making, as well as mentoring. We focus on prevention and early intervention by offering a range of bespoke services, which can be tailored to suit individual and group needs. The projects teach young</p>	
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						people new skills in the creative arts, whilst addressing issues around self confidence, self esteem and general wellbeing by exploring self expression in a fully supported environment	
Organisation Name	Date set up	Bio	Place	Activity	Target Group	Aims	Source
5.6. Phoenix Alternative Music	2019	Phoenix Alternative Music is a non-profit community project which allows Former far-right	UK (online) via Exit Hate, London UK.	Raising awareness to the impact of extremism through music making	Individuals who have	Phoenix Alternative Music allows Former far-right activists to create	https://www.exithub.org/music

		<p>activists to create music however they want to raise awareness of the impact of extremism, but also help activists release their feelings and show what they are thinking today, what involvement is like and how people can change.</p>				<p>music however they want to raise awareness of the impact of extremism, but also help activists release their feelings and show what they are thinking today, what involvement is like and how people can change.</p>	
<p>5.7. Oddarts –</p>	<p>2004</p>	<p><i>Odd Arts is an alumni of the US Embassy Exchange on Countering Violent Extremism.</i></p>	<p>Manchester, England. UK</p>	<p>Odd Arts uses theatre to challenge inequalities & increase opportunities for people facing the greatest level of discrimination & disadvantage.</p>	<p>Disadvantaged groups & Offenders of</p>	<p>Reduce risk of (re) offending Build more cohesive and safer communities Improve mental well</p>	<p>https://oddarts.co.uk/</p>

		<p><i>They focus on wider issues relating more broadly to risk of radicalisation, including: Additional Needs; Domestic/partner abuse; Sexual assault & consent; Knife crime; Exploitation & Mental Health.</i></p>		<p>They work in three ways: Therapeutic theatre workshops to reduce risk; Interactive theatre tours to empower & educate; Creative & community led social action projects to overcome inequalities.</p>	<p>radicalisation</p>	<p>being including increased confidence and self worth Improve work based skills through accreditation, communication skills and therapeutic learning Increase access and engagement to the arts and culture for disadvantaged groups</p>	
<p>Organisation Name</p>	<p>Date set up</p>	<p>Bio</p>	<p>Place</p>	<p>Activity</p>	<p>Target Group</p>	<p>Aims</p>	<p>Source</p>

<p>5.8. Show Racism the Red Card</p>	<p>1990</p>	<p>Show Racism the Red Card is an anti-racism educational charity. We aim to combat racism through enabling role models, who are predominately but not exclusively footballers, to present an anti-racist message to young people and others. Show Racism the Red Card acknowledges that racism changes, as do the experiences of Black, Asian and minority ethnic communities in the</p>	<p>UK – North Shields; Essex; Manchester England, Glasgow, Scotland & Cardiff, Wales.</p>	<p>Football activities & programmes</p>	<p>Inclusive to all</p>	<p>Producing educational Resources.</p> <p>Developing activities to help people, including young people, to challenge racism.</p> <p>Use sports, including football to challenge racism</p>	<p>https://www.theredcard.org/</p>
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		UK. Our message and activities therefore need to be able to respond to such changes as and when appropriate.					

Appendix 2 – Example – showing how data was collated for map entry from Israel.

1. Appendix - Israel		D8.3 arts and sports related social inclusion activities in selected D.Rad sites					
Organization name	Date set up	Bio	Place	Activity	Target Group	Aims	
1.1 Football 4 Peace-Is	2001	(NGO) It began in peri	International/Tel Aviv	"Off-pitch manual"	Jewish and Arab Youth	One of the guiding principles c	https://www.football4peace.org.uk/projects/israel/
1.2 Kicking Racism and	2003	(NGO) Founded by the	Jerusalem, Herzilya, Te	The NGO holds Confer	Jewish and Arab footb	aims to eradicate racism and v	https://nif.org.il/kickitout-con-one/
1.3 Athena- the centre	2007	(NGO) operates	Tel Aviv/Local also	Athena acts to	Girls, young women, a	1. Establishing a quantitative	https://www.athenawomen.org.il/english/
1.4 The LGBT sports cl	2008	Established as a small	Semi-national (Tel	The LGBT+ Sports	LGBTQ+, people with a	A proud sports club leads the	https://twitter.com/tvlgbtsports?lang=en
1.5 The Equalizer Grou	2012	The NGO program ope	Semi-national, Tel	Educational sports	Teenagers, kids from t	Create social, gender and geog	https://en.the-equalizer.org/shaar-shivyon/
1.6 Kicking Homophob	2016	This sub-initiative eme	International, local (He	Activity includes	LGBTQ+ players, judge	It attracts crowds from differe	
1.7 Zaza- Community f	2017	(NGO) Zaza (meaning "	Semi-national (North,	Today they help prom	Local populations, the	1. Promoting, encouraging and	https://www.facebook.com/zazawomen/about
1.8 Equal in sport (Sha	2018	This innovative progra	Semi-national, Local (N	Municipalities get fun	Adults and teenagers	The main aim is to increase th	https://schoolsport.co.il/%D7%A9%D7%95%D7%95%D7%99%D7%9D-%D7%91%D7
1.9 Mamanet	2005	The first ever commur	International (Austria,	Mamanet allows moth	Mothers and adult wo	To supply a model for a combi	https://www.mamanet.org.il/viewArticle_en.asp?id=192_
1.10 El Halev	2003	The NGO is the Israeli	Jerusalem, Tel Aviv-	The association opera	Children, youth, wom	It has two goals. 1. teaching p	https://www.elhalev.org/about

Image	Copyright/source
(Figure) 1.1 Football for Peace	© Football for Peace / https://www.flickr.com/photos/145079513@N02/sets/72157671581672925/with/28563796525
(Figure) 1.3 Athena	© AthenaWomen / https://www.athenawomen.org.il/english/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/MG_0038-1.jpg
(Figure) 1.4 the LGBT sports club Tel Aviv	© The LGBT Sports C;ub / https://scontent.ftlv5-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t39.30808-6/339651565_939653387222470_6580885786131252385_n.jpg?nc_cat=104&ccb=1-7&nc_sid=49d041&nc_ohc=N9-k3b8ktN0AX8KJ8on&nc_ht=s
(Figure) 1.5 Queen of the baskets	© The Equalizer Grop / https://www.the-equalizer.org/programs/
(Figure) 1.7 Zaza	© Zaza / https://scontent.ftlv5-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t39.30808-6/362259380_755135019952863_211987664405741161_n.jpg?nc_cat=111&ccb=1-7&nc_sid=5614bc&nc_ohc=gBQCrDBGnt8AX_EljzQ&nc_ht=scontent.ftlv5-1
(Figure) 1.9 Mamanet	© Mamanet / https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=2724273541197399&id=1843043859320376&paipv=0&eav=AfYbs5EtEGHvGcyZaeDMBAF_GDATJMXOVp_HomT_DIO6HI6QesknhodPnSsilWtV8&_rd
(Figure 1) 1.10 El Halev	© ElHalev / https://www.elhalev.org/shop

Appendix 2. example shows data entries, plus images and their source and copyright for Israel.

